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White-Collar Crime

Domina Petric, MD

White-collar crime is a crime committed by a person of respectability and high social status in the course of their occupation. White-collar crimes are difficult to prosecute because they involve sophisticated systems and even many different people. Frauds typically committed are bribery, extortion, fraud, embezzlement, and cybercrime.

White-collar crime has been associated with the educated and affluent ever since the term was first coined in 1949 by sociologist Edwin Sutherland, who defined it as **crime committed by a person of respectability and high social status in the course of their occupation**¹.

White-collar crime is generally non-violent in nature. It is characterized by deceit, concealment, or violation of trust, and includes public corruption, health care fraud, mortgage fraud, securities fraud, money laundering. White-collar scams can destroy a company, devastate families by wiping out their life savings, or cost investors billions of dollars (or even all three). Today's fraud schemes are more sophisticated than ever².

White-collar crimes are difficult to prosecute because they involve sophisticated systems and even many different people.

Frauds typically committed are **bribery, extortion, fraud, embezzlement, cybercrime**³.

In USA the criminal justice system has given up pretending that the crimes of the wealthy are worth taking seriously. In January 2019, white-collar prosecutions fell to their lowest level since researchers started tracking them in 1998. Even within the dwindling number of prosecutions, most are cases against low-level con artists and small-fry financial schemes. Since 2015, criminal penalties levied by the Justice Department have fallen from \$3.6 billion to roughly \$110 million. Illicit profits seized by the Securities and Exchange Commission have reportedly dropped by more than half. In 2018, a year when nearly 19,000 people were sentenced in federal court for drug crimes alone, prosecutors convicted just 37 corporate criminals who worked at firms with more than 50 employees⁴.

Freemasonry is an example of white-collar crime organization. A history and prevalence of secret societies (the Italian Mafia-Freemasonry connection in the 1970s and 1980s) help create conditions of covertness that facilitated Political Criminal Nexus⁵.

A study by Calderoni and Canappele (2009) examined statistical and qualitative evidence of mafia penetration in Southern Italy. Through the construction of a composite crime index from available data (indicators used included mafia murders, confiscated mafia assets, registered mafia conspiracy crimes, number of city councils dissolved-a measure against city councils penetrated by mafia-registered procurement offenses) for 1991-2007 and 2002-2005, the study found that organized crime in the public procurement processes was more concentrated in Calabria and Sicily than in other areas of Southern Italy. The analysis showed that Calabria had the highest incidence rate of crimes associated with the procurement. The study's explanation focuses on the specific of Calabrese organized crime and the role of Freemasonry⁶.

Another author (Andali 2009) explains that the family-based model of territorial control provides Ndrangheta with a strong local foundation. In addition, Freemasonry has enabled Calabrese crime families to

create links with business entities, politicians and individuals in the administrative and judicial apparatus⁷.

One of the few high-profile corruption cases involved a Nice judge, Jean-Paul Renard. The close association of Judge Renard with the local Freemasonry organization had led to multiple cases of corrupt and questionable behavior. Judge Renard was sentenced for having consulted on numerous occasions, police files to obtain background information on candidates who applied to the Grand National Lodge of France⁸.

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